

PLY CURVING TERMINATION: SUPPRESSING DELAMINATION IN TAPERED COMPOSITES

S. Minakuchi¹, N. Takeda²

¹ Graduate School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8656, JAPAN

² Graduate School of Frontier Sciences, The University of Tokyo
5-1-5 Kashiwanoha, Kashiwa, Chiba, 277-8561, JAPAN

Email: minakuchi@smart.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp

Website: <https://sites.google.com/edu.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp/minakuchilab>

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ABSTRACT

Composite tapered sections with ply drop-off are prone to delamination due to stress concentration at the edge of the terminated 0° plies. Currently quite gradual taper angle is used in aircraft composites to suppress delamination, which leads to weight increase. Structural modification that can suppress the stress concentration is necessary to realize further-optimized lightweight structures with steeper taper angles. This study proposes a new approach called “ply curving termination (PCT)” in which local fiber orientation is modified at the edge of the terminated 0° plies. The curved area has significantly low stiffness and thus the stress concentration at the ply edge is suppressed. This paper reports the numerical analysis and experiment to validate the effectiveness of this new concept. In addition, suppression of edge delamination by PCT is also demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a lightweight aircraft composite structure, it is desirable to decrease the plate thickness in low load areas by terminating unnecessary plies (i.e., ply drop-off, Fig. 1). It is possible to significantly save the structural weight by steeply changing the thickness in response to the local load distribution. However, tapered sections with steep taper angles act as initiation points of delamination. It is known that stress concentrates at the edge of the terminated 0° plies that have the fiber direction in parallel to the loading direction [1-3]. As a result, current aircraft composite structures use quite gradual taper angles and have unnecessary thick parts in the low-load areas. Structural modification that can suppress the stress concentration at the edge of the terminated 0° plies is necessary to realize further-optimized lightweight structures with steeper taper angles. The author devised a new approach called “ply curving termination (PCT)” that locally changes the fiber orientation at the edge of the terminated 0° plies [4]. This paper reports the basic study results.

2 PLY CURVING TERMINATION

Figure 2 shows the most basic form of ply drop-off where the 0° ply is laminated on the base laminate. In the conventional part in Fig. 2 (a), in-plane tensile loading induces stress concentration at the edge of the terminated 0° ply and secondary bending due to the eccentric load path along the ply drop-off, which leads to delamination initiation. In contrast, the PCT structure in Fig. 2 (b) has the curved edge that has significantly low stiffness in the loading direction (e.g., when the curved angle is 45° with standard carbon/epoxy, the elastic modulus decreases to about 10%). This modification suppresses the stress concentration and secondary bending at the edge of the terminated ply, so stress is gradually transferred from the base laminate to the terminated ply. In addition, even if delamination occurs from the edge, its propagation is suppressed in the curved area because the stiffness of the delaminated edge is low. Meanwhile, the terminated ply far away from the edge can fulfill the original purpose of strengthening the base laminate because the fiber direction is along the loading direction.

Figure 1: Schematic of tapered section with ply drop-off.

Upper view

Side view

(a) Conventional structure.

Upper view

Side view

(b) Ply curving termination.

Figure 2: Stress concentration at edge of terminated 0° ply.

It is important to note that introduction of PCT into a structure can be automated and is not limited by the molding method and the stacking sequence. In the case of manufacturing using prepreg sheets, for example, it is possible to introduce this curved part by laminating prepreg sheets after shearing only the terminated part in the in-plane direction (Fig. 3).

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analysis was performed to verify the effectiveness of the proposed structure. The model is shown in Fig. 4. Both the base laminate and the terminated ply were 1 mm thick and were made of carbon fiber/epoxy unidirectional material (T700SC/2592, Toray). Two types of models were prepared: a 45° specimen where PCT was applied and the terminal end of 5 mm was curved to 45° direction, and a 0° specimen in which the fiber travels straight to the terminal end. In-plane displacement of 1 mm was applied to the models and the stress-strain state was calculated.

Figure 3: Introducing PCT using prepreg sheets.

Figure 4: Finite element models.

Figure 5: Deformation and out-of-plane stress at edge of terminated ply. Displacement magnification factor is 20.

Figure 5 shows the deformation and the out-of-plane stress distribution at the center in the width direction. Secondary bending due to the eccentric load path along the ply drop-off was suppressed by PCT, and the out-of-plane stress at the edge of the terminated ply was significantly reduced. The stress at the boundary between the curved part and the straight part in the 45° specimen was suppressed as compared with at the edge of the straight part in the 0° specimen, confirming that PCT suppresses stress concentration and the stress is gradually transferred from the thin part to the thick part through the modified ply drop-off.

4 VALIDATION TESTS USING UNIDIRECTIONAL SPECIMENS

Tensile tests of tapered carbon fiber/epoxy specimens (T700SC/2592 prepreg, Toray) were carried out. The schematic of the specimen is depicted in Fig. 6. The base laminate was 8-ply 0° plies (thickness: 1.1 mm), and the details of the ply drop-off is described below. The specimen width b was 25 mm in the static test and 10 mm in the fatigue test. When PCT was applied, lay-up of prepreg sheets was performed after curving the reinforcing fiber to the 45° direction by shearing the end portion (5 mm) of the prepreg sheets laminated in advance.

4.1 Tests with 1-ply terminated layer

First evaluation was carried out using specimens with the simplest configuration. Specifically, a 1-ply terminated layer was laminated on the base laminate and cured without using a cover ply. Three types of specimens were prepared: a 0° specimen in which the fiber direction of the terminated layer was totally along the loading direction, a 45° specimen with the end portion of 5 mm curved, and a Cut 45° specimen where the curved part was cut from the straight part (Fig. 7).

The results of the static strength test are shown in Fig. 8. In the 0° specimen, the terminating layer delaminated when the strain in the thin section reached $11500 \mu\epsilon$, whereas in the case of the 45° specimen the failure occurred at $18000 \mu\epsilon$. So it was found that the static strength was improved by more than 50% by PCT. In contrast, in the Cut 45° specimen, delamination of the straight part occurred from the cut portion (Fig. 8 right) and the strength was the same as the 0° specimen. It was confirmed that the strength increases only when the rigidity of the terminal end portion is reduced and the curved and straight parts are connected with their continuous reinforced fibers. Next, the results of the fatigue test (maximum load 8 kN (corresponding to $6000 \mu\epsilon$ in the thin part), load ratio 0.1, test

Figure 6: Schematic of specimen.

Figure 7: Specimens with 1-ply terminated layer.

Figure 8: Result of static tensile tests.

Figure 9: Result of fatigue tensile tests.

frequency 8 Hz) are shown in Fig. 9. In the 0° specimen and the Cut 45° specimen, the fiber straight part delaminated immediately after the start of the test and the delamination progressed in proportion to the number of loading cycles, whereas in the case of the 45° specimen no delamination occurred up to 500,000 cycles. It was confirmed that fatigue characteristics can be remarkably improved by PCT.

4.2 Tests with taper ratio of 1:5

Next, two types of specimens with the taper ratio of 1:5 were prepared: a 0° specimen with the fiber direction of 0° in the ply drop-off part and a 45° specimen with the fiber direction of 45° (Fig. 10). A single 0° ply covered the ply drop-off part.

The results of the tensile static and fatigue (load ratio 0.1, test frequency 8 Hz) tests are shown in Fig. 11. The white markers indicate that the specimens did not fail. In the static test, final failure occurred in the both types of specimens when the cover ply and the ply drop-off part delaminated from the base laminate. The failure strain in the thin part was 10000 μϵ for the 0° specimen and 12000 μϵ for the 45° specimen, so PCT increased the static strength by 20%. Meanwhile, in the fatigue test, when a maximum load of 6.7 kN that corresponds to 5000 μϵ in the thin part was applied to the 0° specimen, delamination occurred from the terminal edge of the lowermost ply at about 30,000 cycles. In contrast, the 45° specimen did not show any damage even after 1,000,000 cycles. Furthermore, even when the maximum load was increased by 50% (strain in the thin part was 7500 μϵ), delamination did

Figure 10: Cross-section of tapered specimens.

Figure 11: Static and fatigue test results. White markers indicate that specimens did not fail.

not occur after more than 30,000 cycles, confirming that PCT can improve the fatigue characteristic remarkably.

5 VALIDATION TESTS USING QUASI-ISOTROPIC SPECIMENS

Tests using quasi-isotropic specimens were carried out for evaluation in a practical configuration. The shape of the specimen was the same as in Fig. 6, and the stacking sequence was $[45/0/-45/90]_S$ in the thin part and $[45/0/-45/90]_{S2}$ in the thick part. The taper ratio was 5:1, and the cover ply (one ply of 45° prepreg) was applied on the upper surface. In the PCT specimen, 5 mm parts at the end of the 0° plies were curved to the 45° direction (Fig. 12).

The results of the static test and the fatigue test (load ratio 0.1, test frequency 8 Hz) are shown in Fig. 13. The static failure was defined as peeling of the terminated plies and the fatigue failure as cracking of the cover ply. It was confirmed that PCT remarkably improves the static and fatigue strength. Microscopic observation of the tapered part after the test found that in the conventional specimen without PCT delamination generated from the edge of the 0° ply close to the base material propagated along the 0/45 interface below the 0° layer, while in the PCT specimen delamination occurred in the 0/-45 layers above the 0° ply. So PCT changed the failure process, which contributed to the improvement of strength. Delamination suppression effect of PCT was successfully demonstrated in a practical laminate configuration.

Figure 12: Cross-section of quasi-isotropic specimens.

Figure 13: Static and fatigue test results.

Figure 14: Suppression of edge delamination by PCT.

6 SUPPRESSION OF EDGE DELAMINATION USING PCT

PCT is a simple yet powerful technique to suppress delamination from ply edges, so its application is not limited to ply drop-off. One interesting application is suppression of edge delamination. Figure 14 shows a soft X-ray image of quasi-isotropic specimen ($[45/-45/0/90]_s$) after the tensile fatigue test (maximum strain $9000 \mu\epsilon$, load ratio 0.1, 500 cycles). PCT was introduced only at the left side of the specimen, and the edges of the two 90° plies were curved to 45° and -45° directions. It can be clearly seen that edge delamination was suppressed in the curved side, implying that PCT has high potential in composite structural regions other than ply-drop-off.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A new approach PCT was devised to suppress delamination in ply drop-off. Basic investigation was carried out on PCT which locally changes the fiber direction of the terminal end portion and it was successfully demonstrated that the static strength and fatigue characteristics can be remarkably improved. In addition to this, the effectiveness of this approach for suppressing stress concentration at the cover ply (e.g., point A in Fig. 1) has been confirmed and other types of fiber features (e.g., looped fiber structures) have been successfully demonstrated. Future work will address the optimization of the shape and configuration of the curved part and the automated manufacturing of practical structures including PCT.

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